

Understanding the ‘WHY’ of Bitcoin is what advocates need to drive home, as opposed to the investing potential

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

While it’s easy to be excited about the incredible gains that crypto currencies have had, particularly Bitcoin, it’s important to introduce Bitcoin/cryptos to beginners from more of a fundamental basis, as opposed to it being an investment vehicle with great potential.

2. Aim

In order to increase mass adoption, we need to emphasize the reasons *why* Bitcoin and crypto currencies are important. This can include illustrating the current financial system, how blockchain technology works, and the properties of which they possess, making it a better means of exchange of value.

3. Material and methods

Bitcoinbasics.org has been created to break down the learning barriers involved with getting started, as well as providing ample resources to give beginners the education and confidence they need to take the first step. Quality, engaging, informative and free content is provided in most aspects needed for your average person to get started, with a heavy emphasis on *why* Bitcoin is important and will change our lives.

4. Results

To date we have helped x amount of people begin their journey in understanding Bitcoin and we continue to increase that number everyday.

5. Conclusions

With the feedback we’ve received, we’ve determined that simplicity is key in converting your average person into one that can at least begin to learn about Bitcoin, which is the most important part of the process. Bitcoinbasics.org has been designed to help the masses understand this seemingly complex world, from a very fundamental basis, and emphasizes that advocates should also take the same approach.

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6. Keywords

Bitcoin, Crypto currencies, blockchain technology

Author biography

Arash P. Toussi Arash Toussi started is a serial entrepreneur who started his first business at the young age of 20, followed by his second at 25. With an everlasting desire to help people find financial freedom and happiness, he founded his 3rd company, bitcoinbasics.org to help people better understand the system we are currently living in, and how Bitcoin and crypto currencies can help revolutionize our lives for the better. Aside from running bitcoinbasics.org, Arash is an active investor in the ICO and crypto currency space.

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